

SOME BIOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF SPIRULINA BIOMASS

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Abstract: Spirulina is an improvement of the technology of protein and vitamin enrichment of dairy products using algae biomass.

Key words: Spirulina, food product, abiotic and biotic factors, vitamins, protein, yogurt preparation, acid

INTRODUCTION

It is known that in our Republic certain works are being carried out in a systematic manner regarding the production of food products and the provision and development of food safety.

Providing people with nutritious food products rich in all necessary food ingredients, not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the world community, has its own complex stages and requirements related to human health.

Therefore, in order to ensure the stable development of this direction in Uzbekistan, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Quality and Safety of Food Products" was adopted (1997) and is widely used in the regulation of all current processes.

But since last year, under the influence of emerging abiotic and biotic factors, there are a number of problems in fully satisfying the population's demand for food products in local conditions. Including

1. The land area used for agriculture in our country increased from 28080.4 thousand hectares in 1990 to 25621.6 thousand hectares in 2015, i.e. -2458.8 thousand hectares, correspondingly, the arable land area decreased from 4176.5 thousand hectares to 4043.6 thousand hectares, i.e. - to 132.9 thousand hectares, irrigated land from 3407.3 thousand hectares to 3288.2 thousand hectares, i.e. - 119.1 thousand

hectares, and agricultural arable land from 4200.1 thousand hectares to 3694.2 thousand hectares, i.e. -505.9 thousand hectares shortened [N.I. Saidahmedova].

This indicates that ensuring food safety is of urgent importance.

2. The composition of food products produced in practice remains extremely low for people of a certain age group, for example, only bread and salt products are produced for a specific group of the population, and the production rate is not equal to the total production potential - It is 0.2-0.3%. While iodized salt products are 100% produced, bread products for diabetics with several brand names make up 0.02% of the total production.

3. Although the production of milk and dairy products has been widely implemented in local conditions, taking into account young children and age groups, only one indicator of these products, namely the fat content indicator, has been taken into account.

Due to the fact that other indicators are not taken into account, the demand for the most necessary ingredients in the growth phase of young children remains unmet.

4. Due to the use of various ingredients instead of natural products in the composition of milk and dairy products produced for children or in dietary forms, the incidence of avitaminosis, anemia, and various forms of rickets in children is increasing day by day.

For this reason, to study the possibilities of fully meeting the children's need for vitamins and protein by preparing the archival part of yogurt, which is the main dairy product that is the main favorite of children under the age of 5, who make up the majority of the local population, and is rich in vitamins and proteins. and on the basis of alternative sources with low production costs, one of the urgent tasks is to enrich the content of dairy products with proteins and vitamins.

One of the above-mentioned urgent problems, i.e., one of the non-traditional sources that are widely used to enrich the composition of food products with proteins and vitamins, is SPIRULINA algae.

The novelty of the work

- For the first time, local isolates of Spirulina algae have been algologically isolated and their taxonomic position has been established based on molecular genetic methods (16S ribosomal RNA);
- For the first time, the morpho-cultural and some biochemical characteristics of Arthrospira platensis TKTI Uz-03, Spirulina laxissima TKTI Uz-106 and Spirulina subsalsa TKTI Uz-76 strains purified locally were characterized;
- For the first time, the taxonomic position of Arthrospira platensis TKTI Uz-03, Spirulina laxissima TKTI Uz-106 and Spirulina subsalsa TKTI Uz-76 strains of Spirulina algae was determined and included in the international NCBI (GenBank) database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Dehydration of lipid composition of Spirulina subsalsa TKTI Uz-76 fraction at different temperatures (% lipids relative to total mass)

Dehydration temperature	Total lipid content of the dry extract	lipid fraction		
		phospholipids	unsaturated fatty acids	saturated fatty acids
30	11.3	100.0	-	-
60	14.0	68.2	22.9	8.9
70	27.3	80.5	19.5	-

This distribution of lipid composition can be explained by the fact that phospholipids are the main component of the biomembrane. It is known that the reconstruction of the membrane structure depends significantly on phospholipids.

Dehydration at 30°C corresponds to the optimal physiology of *Spirulina subsalsa* TKTU Uz-76 strain, and therefore it was observed that the lipid composition did not change as much as possible.

Total fatty acid composition of *Spirulina laxissima* TKTU Uz-106 strain

Fatty acids	10 mg	total retention in %
myristin	1	0.2%
palmitin	244	45.0%
palmitolein	33	5.6%
hectocarbon	2	0.3%
Stearin	8	1.4%
Olein	12	2.2%
Linolin	97	17.9%
gamma-Linolin	135	24.9%
Others	14	2.5%
Total sum	546	100%

METHODS OF OBTAINING LOCAL MICROALGAE

Growth media of unicellular green algae

The following nutrient media were used for the isolation and cultivation of native unicellular green algae (microalgae):

1. "Chu - 13" nutrient medium (g/l): KNO_3 – 0.2, K_2HPO_4 – 0.04, $\text{MgSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.1, $\text{CaCl}_2 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.08, iron citrate – 0.01, citric acid – 0.1, boron – 0.5 ppm, $\text{MnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.5 ppm, $\text{CuSO}_4 \times 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.02 ppm, $\text{CoCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.02 ppm, $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.02 ppm, pH 7.5.

2. "Tamiya" nutrient medium (g/l): KNO_3 – 5, $\text{MnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 2.5, KH_2PO_4 – 1.25, $\text{FeSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.003, EDTA – 0.037, mixture of trace elements – 1 ml.

Microelements (g/l): H_3BO_3 – 2.86, $\text{MnCl}_2 \times 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 1.81, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \times 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – 0.222, MoO_3 – 176.4 mg/10 l, NH_4VO – 229.6 mg/10 l.

Obtaining local microalgae aggregate cultures. In order to obtain collective cultures of local microalgae, water samples brought from Andijan region were added to sterile 100 ml "Chu-13" liquid nutrient medium and shaken at a temperature of 26o-28oS and light of 3500-4000 Lk. The samples began to turn visually green in 14-20 days, allowing them to be seen under a light microscope. Stock cultures of microalgae were grown to a titer of 10^3 h/ml. After that, they were diluted up to 100 times and planted in 2% agar media and grown at 26o-28oC temperature and 3500-4000 Lk light. The formed microalgae colonies were isolated by repeated cultivation in liquid mineral nutrient medium.

Obtaining pure algal isolates. The methods used by Shakirov and Safarov in the selection and purification of microalgae were carried out in the order reflected in the scientific sources published by them. In particular, the suspension of microalgae isolates was diluted and spread on the top surface of the agar nutrient medium in a Petri dish using a sterile spatula and exposed to light of 3500–4000 Lk until the growth of microalgae colonies.

Grown microalgae colonies were collected using a microbiological hook and transferred to liquid nutrient medium. These methods were repeated several times (6-8 times) and as a result local unicellular green algae were isolated in algologically and bacteriologically clean form.

Screening of indigenous microalgae. Isolation of active forms of microalgae were selected according to their growth rate, colony size and biomass production in agar medium and liquid medium.

The first method: the algal suspension was spread on a standard agar medium and the diameter of the resulting microalgal colonies was measured in an ocular-micrometer. Colonies with a high growth rate were isolated.

The second method: in order to select the active forms of algae, it is determined according to their biomass production rate, for which microalgae are grown in the same liquid nutrient medium and under the same conditions. The amount of microalgae biomass produced is sampled by measuring it on an analytical balance.

SUMMARY AND SIGNIFICANCE

1. It is determined by determining the composition of the moderate nutrient medium and cultivation conditions for industrial cultivation of isolated spirulina strains;
2. It is explained by the development and implementation of the technology of spirulina biomass cultivation and application in the process of making yogurt;
3. Spirulina - the composition of yogurt from dairy products using algae biomass is of practical importance due to the fact that it is enriched with proteins and vitamins.

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